

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

DIGITAL TWIN OF POSTGRADUATE EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION: ECOSYSTEM FOR TRANSFORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHERS IN CONDITIONS OF MARTIAL LAW

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Abstract

The article highlights new views on possibilities of transformation of teachers' professional development in the system of postgraduate education in conditions of war and other crisis situations. It is shown that these possibilities are also conditioned by transition from learning management systems (LMS) to next generation digital learning environment (Next Generation Digital Learning Environment (NGDLE) regarded as an ecosystem of digital tools to support the activities of participants in educational process. For the first time, the authors reveal the NGDLE environmental features, which characterize NGDLE as an open, stable, safe and comfortable system for participants in educational process, as well as system ensuring the exchange of information between separate participants and/or between separate participants and the world around them. Such digital ecosystems are created in format of digital twins of real postgraduate educational institutions in order to ensure the continuity of education and professional development of teachers. Practical implementation of such of new generation concepts is shown on the example of Ukrainian Open University of Postgraduate Education (<https://uvu.org.ua>).

Keywords: digital twin, digital ecosystem, professional development, transformation of professional development, postgraduate education, teachers, open university, crisis situation, crisis conditions.

Unfortunately, many countries around the world are facing the problems of educational crisis during the war, as well as the problems caused by other factors, such as natural disasters, epidemics and so on. The educational system in Ukraine has been functioning in crisis conditions for several years in a row.

While the quarantine restrictions caused by the COVID-19 epidemic have not still expired, Ukraine has got one more challenge to overcome – the country stepped into the period of martial law introduced due to military aggression of Russian Federation.

In these conditions, the continuity aspect of education provided for children and youth becomes especially important. Education helps to bridge the gap between stable past and new present being. In this regard the professionalism of teachers becomes an important factor.

In war conditions the competencies of managers and teachers of educational institutions require significant rapid changes, which we consider as transformation of professional development.

War and other crisis situations cause a drastic break in established norms and stereotypes in regard of professional activity of teachers, at the same time crisis situations can disable the performance of certain functions by teachers and produce negative effect on mental state of participants in educational process.

Therefore, despite all current negative effects, and in order to ensure and maintain the functioning of country's educational system, it is necessary to prioritize the transformation of professional development of educators (both managers and teachers) so that they could quickly acquire those competencies that will form the basis for professional activity in new, unusual, uncertain, dangerous conditions.

In this article we would like to consider the possibility of using digital technologies for transformation and continuous support of teachers' professional development.

Current events taking place in modern pedagogical world show that educational system is acquiring the features of electronic resource used for digital learning. In this context, the transformation of postgraduate education is developing accordingly. Its methodology is changing and acquiring fundamentally new features, namely: demand for support of professional development of educators, based on combination of such factors: as usage of personal experience, mastering of modern effective technologies, update of educational content, communication in the system of subject-to-subject relations.

Also, current events taking place in society, in particular the war in Ukraine, show that it is essential for the state to be prepared and possess adequate resources

to ensure the continuity of teachers education. Accordingly, the teachers must be ready to have training provided in view of modern technologies in general. After all, they are responsible for the future of the state.

The International Rescue Committee (IRC) has recently published a list of 2022 emergencies – a global list of «humanitarian crises expected to worsen during the next year» [6]. Most of surveyed countries have been experiencing the period of continuous conflicts over past decade. This factor has complicated their ability to respond to global challenges such as COVID-19 and climate changes. 20 countries placed at the beginning of this list home 10% of world's population, but 89% of this segment is in need of humanitarian assistance.

Actually, the website features «10 biggest crises that cannot be ignored by the world in the year of 2022». However, on March 1, 2022, the editor added the following remark: «The list of 2022 emergencies was compiled before Russia's invasion to Ukraine». In view of current situation in Ukraine, the authors propose to add Ukraine to this list and to put it in the first position, namely – position 0. As a result, the list corrected by the authors will look like this (numbering from top to bottom):

10. Sudan – Political tensions in combination with regional drought and conflicts.

9. Syria – Economic crisis follows the decade of war.

8. Somalia – Access to humanitarian aid is complicated proportionally to increasing needs.

7. Myanmar – Dead end situation results in increase of impoverishment.

6. Democratic Republic of Congo – conflicts and diseases are combined with crisis.

5. South Sudan – regional tensions increase risks.

4. Nigeria –growing insecurity reported all over the country.

3. Yemen – experiences cumulative effect of long-lasting conflict.

2. Ethiopia – experiences critical situation due to combination of climate challenges and ethnic conflicts.

1. Afghanistan – experiences post-conflict crisis

0. Ukraine – Russia's violent full-scale invasion to Ukraine brings global destruction of all components of state infrastructure (social, engineering, medical, transport, education and other industries).

The purpose of the article is to present the idea that the impact of crisis situations urges the necessity to create digital ecosystems such as NGDLE, designed for teachers' professional development in digital twins of postgraduate educational institutions.

The novelty of presented results of theoretical and practical research on transformation of postgraduate education in crisis conditions lies in introduction of new concept to scientific circulation – a digital ecosystem; the article contains substantiation of ideas of NGDLE type ecosystems usage for professional development of teachers in digital twins of postgraduate educational institutions.

A crisis is regarded as drastic change and aggravation of situation, critical detection of contradictions in

socio-economic system or inside particular organization, which threatens its stability in the environment and makes it impossible to perform functions normally [11; 12].

The generalized experience of introduction of digital learning in postgraduate education indicates its advantages for:

- educational institutions (EI) – providing a wide range of users with open access to electronic educational resources (EER);

- teachers – ensuring effective focus on educational activities with lower costs of organizational activities; continuous improvement of personal level of digital competencies.

It is known that postgraduate education provides teachers with new opportunities to be involved in educational activities, regardless of their place of residence, as well as to choose and implement an individual trajectory of professional development. However, it should be noted that in digital society, the understanding of term “digital learning” may slightly differ for various educational institutions. In general, this is a fairly broad concept, which covers the forms and formats of educational process, software, teaching methods, electronic educational resources and etc. Since these components are in process of dynamic development in accordance with specifics of digital resources, it is necessary to define the conditions for creation of innovative learning environment, which at the same time unites them into a single system and stays open for changes and renewals [8].

It should be noted that in recent years, the scientists have developed a vision of next generation digital learning environment NGDLE as an extremely adapted ecosystem of digital tools used to support the activities of participants in educational process [5].

Researcher Michael Feldstein notes that the term NGDLE was adopted to denote what should follow the era of LMS (Learning management system) [7]. The authors use this term to combine several key points.

First, the future of education should acquire a new model focused on learning with accent made on learning practices applicable for future generation.

Second, future education must be digitally based, given that digital technologies have practically become structural component of all teaching and learning practices.

Third, it must exist in a format of educational environment or holistic and dynamic ecosystem, characterized by sustainable development as a community of participants in educational process, tools and educational content.

«The basic message of NGDLE research is that all participants in educational process must have the ability to shape and adjust their learning environment according to personal needs and tasks. By supporting component architecture based on standards and best practices, NGDLE encourages the research into new approaches and development of new tools» [5].

Earlier the EDUCAUSE and The Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation have already launched an «investigation into what this next-generation education system might look like. Its main functional areas were:

compatibility, personalization, analytics, consulting and evaluation, cooperation, availability and universal design. Since no program can cover all these areas simultaneously, the authors recommend a Lego approach to NGDLE implementation, which builds NGDLE-compliant components that enable individuals and institutions to create learning environments according to their requirements and goals [4].

Initially it was the spread of COVID-19 pandemic, as a factor of crisis situation in Ukrainian education, that encouraged the authors to start a search for innovative solutions. Further on, the treacherous war launched by Russia against Ukraine gave us another powerful impulse to develop our research.

It is during the crisis that the need for qualified personnel increases significantly. After all, highly qualified managerial, pedagogical, scientific – pedagogical staff are able to overcome the crisis and its consequences. The crisis causes the problems related to ensuring stable functioning of professional development system, its management, finding new opportunities for maintaining of educational process and scientific /methodological activities without reducing the quality of education [8, p. 1].

As mentioned above, LMS are quite popular – now they occupy key positions in organization of digital learning. The results of series of EDUCAUSE and ECAR surveys show that the majority of students were satisfied with LMS at their EI and wished the LMS to be used for other courses of the curriculum. Respondents also indicated some aspects to be improved, namely those related to communication, collaboration, relationships, personalization, and mobile accessibility.

We can see that LMS weak points (related to organization of current processes in postgraduate education) observed both in the past and at present, coincide. After all, in crisis conditions, the concept of postgraduate education requires complete reconsideration of digital learning importance. The results of analytical research indicate that possible solution may be the development of NGDLE, which will include the DT capabilities and allow to model innovative pedagogical approaches to organization of educational process.

Following in the footsteps of foreign researchers, we will try to answer the question «Why do we switch from LMS to NGDLE»? If LMS is regarded a «one size fitting all» [5], then NGDLE is an ecosystem.

All above mentioned makes a pretext for the following concept: online postgraduate trainers of future will never agree to limitations set to developing their courses entirely within the LMS. This thesis is confirmed by the results of the study by EDUCAUSE and the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, which identified gaps between modern LMS and digital learning environment that could meet the changing needs of education.

What exactly motivates us to regard NGDLE as ecosystem? At first glance, gadgets and digital technologies are the opposite of wildlife and anti-environmental. Even in society, particularly in education, there is a widespread perception that the digital world is harmful to humans.

In order to characterize NGDLE as an ecosystem, let us recall that an ecological system (deriving from Greek Οἶκος – home, habitat and Greek σύστημα – system) is a collection of living organisms (biocenosis) that have adapted to living together in a certain habitat (biotope), forming a single whole with it.

Based on this, we will try to identify and characterize the properties of NGDLE that make it related to ecosystems. In a broad sense, eco-, environmental friendliness – means unity with nature, human being harmless to nature, as well as favor of natural factors and natural environment for human being. In pedagogy, such approaches are reflected in the principle of environmental education and upbringing of children (J.A. Comenius, J-J. Rousseau, I.G. Pestalozzi, K. Ushinsky, V. Sukhomlinsky).

If we draw an analogy between the ecosystem and NGDLE, we can say that it can be considered as an environment where a person, teacher, child, any participant in educational process in conditions of favorable environment, acquires the necessary knowledge together with other people – tutors, mentors, teachers, consultants, coaches. At the same time, a group of people has an opportunity for both group interaction in learning process and individual work.

NGDLE regarded as ecosystem is a place where digital resources and people coexist. The collection of people is analogous to the biocenosis (collection of living organisms), the digital environment is analogous to the biotope (common home, environment of coexistence). Digital environment and people form a whole and in this sense it can be regarded as ecosystem. People in digital ecosystem must adapt to its specific features while digital environment must be safe and comfortable for people; that is a condition for coexistence. NGDLE has certain features in common with ecosystems, namely:

- operation under certain conditions;
- signs of open systems (exchange of resources with the environment, free entry and exit of participants);
- provision and support the exchange of information;
- Inclusion of structures for obtaining primary information;
- inclusion of structures that convert primary information and enable the system functioning;
- safety and comfort for each participant in educational process;
- stability, ability to maintain structure and function under the influence of external factors;
- vulnerability (possible harm from external factors or possible adaptation to new conditions).

Researchers describe NGDLE as «a loose network of diverse components designed for mutual work – a «confederation of IT systems and application components which comply with general technical standards. This combination would provide diversity and consistency». NGDLE can be also defined as «dynamic and interconnected community of participants in educational process with usage of constantly evolving tools and content»[1].

According to this concept, education is becoming a dynamic digital resource reinforced by interconnection of content, systems, tools, artificial intelligence and virtual reality. The authors consider that the term Digital twin is the most suitable for definition of this resource. Earlier, a well-known research company Gartner predicted that «by 2021 half of all large industrial companies will use DT, and it will lead to 10% increase in their efficiency».

It was found that DT technology is being increasingly used in advanced industries to achieve various goals. According to research by Deloitte, DT technology is spreading rapidly in such industries such as aerospace, retail, healthcare and more. In industry, DTs are used to optimize the operation and maintenance of physical systems and production processes, where digital twins are understood as digital copies of physical models whose behavior (digital and physical) can be observed simultaneously in real time mode. Developed DTs are designed either to visualize objects or to evaluate technological solutions.

Digital representation of objects provides both the development of individual elements and the dynamics of functioning of physical analogue. In industrial sector, there are functioning too many digital twins of equipment, systems, separate machines, or even entire enterprises, which are being developed preliminary to launching of large-scale and high-speed production [2]. That is, DTs can imitate any aspect of a physical object or process. There exist several definitions for the term Digital Twin [3]:

- digital representation of real object or system;
- software analogue of physical device that simulates internal processes, technical characteristics and behavior of real object under the influence of obstacles and environment;
- progressing fundamental technologies which cover both physical and digital spheres and enable obtaining increasingly important digital results;
- digital copy of living or non-living physical object;
- digital replica (imprint) of potential and actual physical values, processes, people, places, systems and devices.

First of all, due to DT technology, digital twins of educational institution can become a dynamic structure, which is growing and constantly evolving in parallel with real one. Similarly, there is a possibility to create a web resource for postgraduate educational institution in digital twin format, which should help the following categories

- administrative staff:
 - to keep all components of educational process under control;
 - to provide single environment for data contained in different systems and functions;
 - to analyze operational data on implementation of;
 - to outline opportunities for improvement of educational process quality;
- teaching staff:
 - to carry out educational process;
- learners:

- to get access to quality education due to the usage of powerful resources.

However, the existence of these advantages does not mean the ease of building and maintaining DT version of postgraduate educational institution today – it is rather complex and continuous process. For example, there may occur the difficulties related to technological and technical problems, as well as to preservation of copyright and personal data of participants in educational process [10].

Nowadays digital transformation is closely connected with Internet of Things, involvement of artificial intelligence, augmented and virtual reality. All these factors become new tools for learning, and it surely allows to suggest that the process of developing digital analogues of EI, namely their digital twins, has already begun. Today the world is using the power of digital technology to gain a broad understanding of activities performed by business sector and individual employees, as well as the technologies and tools they use. It is possible that modern education is in the process of reformation, when the image of any EI without digital twin structure will seem incomplete. Nowadays we can surely state that each citizen, company or individual institution already has got its own digital image – a web image that is being continuously formed into digital twin.

DT version is being formed according to its individual trajectory paved in spaces of Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn and others. The web image is amplified with information available in electronic health care system, trading companies, electronic educational resources, government resources and others, used by the entity and reflecting its activities. When it comes to personal web image, a dynamic web prototype which represents the system of his competencies is being created.

As mentioned above, the urgency of creating NGDLE for training has increased due to long period of quarantine restrictions and war in Ukraine (2022). There appeared new factors which prompted the creation of NGDLE ecosystem in the format of Web-portal that is the digital twin of real educational institution: uncertainty as to further course of events and remoteness of participants in educational process. This web-portal provides not only for training and professional development of specialists, but also for proper quality of educational process management.

Thus, current trends in postgraduate education together with crisis situations dictated the necessity to create qualitatively new model and conditions for professional development of teachers; there has been created a digital twin of Central Institute of Postgraduate Education (CIPE ecosystem). Technologically this ecosystem is variable, differentiated, personality-oriented structure functioning in view of digital world opportunities.

CIPE ecosystem – Web-portal Ukrainian open university of postgraduate education – is a digital resource designed to organize and support non-formal postgraduate education (Picture 1. <https://uvu.org.ua>).

It has become a complex of digital solutions aimed at realization of following priorities: successful operation of virtual departments (Picture 2), continuous implementation of educational process (an authentic edu-

ational environment was created for this purpose (Picture 3), professional development of students (thematic webinars), coverage of innovative educational practices, etc.

Picture 1. Ukrainian open university of postgraduate education

Picture 2. Virtual departments of Ukrainian open university of postgraduate education

Picture 3. Authentic educational environment of Ukrainian open university of postgraduate education

Given that the DT theory existed in various fields for more than a decade, the authors think that it should be considered as a state-of-the-art web tool for professional development in crisis conditions. After all, DTs allow to combine methods, forms, tools, content and systems that in synergy will optimize and modernize the educational process, and consequently will lead to obtaining of quality results in postgraduate education.

The identified trends in creation of DT and formation of ecosystem indicate that Ukrainian educational system is expected to enter the stage of innovative changes adaptable to crisis conditions. Ukrainian open university of postgraduate education is an indispensable innovative resource which unites Ukrainian educators focused on quality teaching and obtaining quality educational results.

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